

Computer- aided Diagnosis of Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm after Endovascular Repair Using Texture Analysis

G. García¹, J. Maiora² A. Tapia¹, M. De Blas³

¹Systems Engineering and Automatic Control Department –EUP, University of the Basque Country, San Sebastián, Spain.

²Electronics and Telecommunications Department –EUP, University of the Basque Country, San Sebastián, Spain.

³Radiology Department, Donostia Hospital, San Sebastián, Spain.

Abstract.

Endovascular repair is a minimal invasive alternative to open surgical therapy. From a long term perspective, complications such as prostheses displacement or leaks inside the aneurysm sac (endoleaks) could appear influencing the evolution of treatment. The objective of this work is to develop a preliminary Computer-aided diagnosis system (CAD) for an automated classification of EVAR progression from computed tomography angiography CTA images. The system is based on the extraction of texture features from thrombus aneurysm samples and a posterior classification. Regions of interest (ROIs) from patients with different post-EVAR evolution were extracted by experienced radiologists. Three conventional texture-analysis methods such as the gray level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM), the gray level run length matrix (GLRLM), and the gray level difference method (GLDM), were applied to each ROI to obtain texture features. Classification of the ROI is carried out by three different strategies. In the first one each feature set is fed to a neural network (NN). The second consists of a single neural network fed with a reduced version of texture features after a feature selection process. The third one comprised an ensembles of classifiers (ECs), formed by three NNs, each using as input one of the feature sets. The final decision is based on the application of a voting scheme across the outputs of the individual NNs. Classification results from the three classification strategies are evaluated using a receiver operating-characteristics (ROC) analysis and area under the roc curve (A_z) performance. The multiple classification scheme using the three sets of texture features results in a better performance, as compared to the classification performance of the other alternatives.

Keywords— Aneurysm, EVAR, texture features, ensembles of classifiers

1 Introduction

The endovascular prostheses in Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm has proven to be an effective technique to reduce the pressure and rupture risk of aneurysm, offering shorter post-operation recovery than open surgical repair. The Endovascular Aneurysm Repair (EVAR) treatment, is a percutaneous image-guided endovascular procedure in which a stent graft is inserted into the aneurysm cavity. Once the stent is placed, the blood clots around the metallic mesh forcing the blood flux through the stent and reducing the pressure on the aneurysm walls consequently. Nevertheless, in a long term perspective different complications such as prostheses displacement or leaks inside the aneurysm sac (endoleaks) could appear provoking a pressure elevation and increasing the danger of rupture consequently. Due to this, periodic follow-up scans of the prosthesis behaviour are necessary. At present, contrast enhanced computed tomographic angiography (CTA) is the most commonly used examination for imaging surveillance [1]. On the other hand, the post operation analysis is quite crude as it involves manually measuring different physical parameters of the aneurysm cavity. According to these measurements, the evolution of the aneurysm can be split up into two main categories:

- Favourable evolution. A reduction of the diameter of the aneurysm sac can be observed. This means that the aneurysm has been correctly excluded from the circulation.
- Unfavourable evolution. A growth of the aneurysm diameter is observed. Endoleaks can sometimes be detected thanks to contrast in the CT images.

Regarding the unfavourable evolution cases we can also distinguish a particular situation. There are patients in which abdominal aneurysm does not increase or reduce significantly its volume and endoleaks are not visually detected (endotensión). Even today the cause for this behaviour remains a source of controversy [2].

According to our previous studies [3], texture thrombus in favourable shrinking aneurysms differs from unfavourable expanding or stable ones. A CAD system based on texture analysis can help clinicians to determine the evolution of mass thrombus inside the aneurysm sac, particularly in ambiguous aneurysm evolution cases. This is clinically important because a more complete assessment of EVAR progression would be useful in re-defining patients management [2].

In recent years, many efforts have been put into the developing of Computer -Aided Diagnosis (CAD) systems based on image processing methods. The principal motivation for the research on this kind of systems has been to assist the clinicians on the analysis of medical images, [5]. In many occasions this analysis implies the detection or measurement of subtle differences, usually difficult to appreciate by visual inspection even for experienced radiologist. CAD systems have been successfully utilized in a wide range of medical applications [6-8]. A particular field inside the image processing methods for CAD systems is the so named texture-based analysis. This analysis studies, not only the variation of the pixel intensity values along the image but also the possible spatial arrangement of them, and the more or less periodic repetition of such arrangement (primitives). From this point of view texture analysis can help on

the functional characterization of different kind of organs, tissues, etc, at the evolution of disease. The textures features obtained from the analysis can be fed as inputs for a deterministic or probabilistic classifier, which assign each sample with its specific class.

Textures analysis methods can generally be classified into three categories: statistical methods, model based methods, and structural methods [9]. In our approach we have focused on the application of statistical texture methods, specifically, on spatial domain statistical techniques as the Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM) [10], the Gray Level Run Length Matrix (GLRLM) [11] and the Gray Level Difference Method (GLDM) [12]. These three extended methods can capture second or higher order statistics on the relation between gray values in pixel pairs or groups of pixels in order to estimate their probability-density functions. Their validity has been proved in many studies [13- 15]. In the last years, multiple classifier architecture has been proposed to improve the performance of CAD systems [16-17]. In multiple classifier systems, also called classifier ensembles (EC), an initial prediction is made by several separate classifiers and then fused into one final assessment through a combining strategy [18].

Our purpose in this study is to develop a preliminary support system based on textures analysis which provides clinicians with complementary information for correctly classifying EVAR treatment evolution. This is clinically important because a more complete assessment of EVAR progression would be useful in re-defining management pathways for patients, particularly when new treatment options are available [4].

The paper is organised as follows: "Materials and Methods" provides with information about the acquisition of CTA images, the theoretical background on the texture analysis methods, and the definition of neural network architectures contemplated in the implementation of the CAD system. The methodology, and results obtained from the performance evaluation of the classifiers are presented in "Results". Finally, some conclusions are given in "Conclusion" section.

2 Materials and methods

2.1 Dataset

The CTA image scans used in this work were obtained by a group of 3 experienced radiologists from the Vascular Surgery Unit and Interventional Radiology Department of the Donostia Hospital. These CTA images belong to the scan studies of 90 patients with ages ranging from 65 to 93 years, conducted over a maximum of 5 years in fixed periods of 6-12 months.

The total patient set was selected by each one of the radiologist, unaware of each others results. In order to generate ground-truth data sets only cases with complete agreement on classification among all radiologists were selected. Balanced samples sets for training and testing the classifier system were obtained. A total of 45 CTA studies belonged to the "favourable evolution" class and 45 to the "unfavourable" one. All the studies were taken from the abdominal area with a spatial resolution of 512×512 pixels and 12-bit gray-level at the WW400 y WL40 window and 5 mm

thickness in DICOM format. For each patient a maximum of three ROIs (15x15 pixels) from aneurysm thrombus were manually extracted from different slices by radiologists, resulting in a total of 270 ROIs. Half of them corresponded to the "favourable evolution" group and the rest to the "unfavourable" one.

2.2 Texture Analysis - Feature Extraction

Gray Level Co-occurrence Matrix (GLCM).

The gray level co-occurrence matrix (GLCM) [10] is an estimation of a second order joint conditional probability density function $f(i,j|d, \theta)$. This function characterizes the spatial interrelationships of the gray values in an image. The values of the co-occurrence matrix elements represent the probability of going from gray level i to gray level j given that they are separated by the distance d and the direction is given by the angle θ (usually $\theta = 0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, \text{ and } 135^\circ$). For computing this probability the image is scanned in direction θ and the co-occurrences accumulated in the GLCM. GLCM features are extracted for 'n×n' primitive template matrix in the directions $0^\circ, 45^\circ, 90^\circ, \text{ and } 135^\circ$, and in some cases, averaging is done to make them direction invariant.

In the present application, GLCM features have been calculated at distance 1 due to the reduced size of the aneurysm samples. Initially, the assumption of an isotropic texture distribution inside the aneurysm sac was considered, consequently averaging over the four angular directions was computed. To reduce the influence of random noise on texture features, the number of gray levels was reduced to 16 prior to the accumulation of the matrix. From GLCM matrix a set of features are obtained to classify the kind of texture analysed. In this study, 13 features have been evaluated: Energy, correlation, inertia, entropy, inverse difference moment, sum average, sum variance, sum entropy, difference average, difference variance, difference entropy and two information measures of correlation.

The Gray Level Run Length Matrix (GLRLM).

The gray level run length matrix (GLRLM) [11] higher order statistical texture information. For a given image, a run length matrix is a two-dimensional matrix in which each element $p(i,j/\theta)$ represents the total number of runs with pixels of gray value i and run length j in a certain direction θ . The number of gray levels in the image is usually reduced by re-quantization before the accumulation of the matrix. Averaging over the four angular directions was computed and the number of gray levels has been kept in 16, equal than in the GLCM method in order to make both methods comparable. Various textures features can then be extracted from the run length matrix. In our case the following 11 features has been calculated: short run emphasis, long run emphasis, gray-level non-uniformity, run length non-uniformity, run percentage, low gray-level run emphasis, high gray-level run emphasis, short run low gray-level emphasis, short run high gray-level emphasis, long run low gray-level emphasis, and long run high gray-level emphasis.

Gray Level Difference Method.

The Gray Level Difference method (GLDM) [12] based on the occurrence of two pixels which have a given absolute difference in gray level and which are separated by a specific displacement δ , estimated by the probability-density function $D(i/\delta)$. In this analysis, four possible forms of the vector δ will be considered: $(0, d)$, $(-d, d)$, $(d, 0)$, and $(d, -d)$ where d is the intersample spacing distance. Due to the reduced size of the aneurysm samples, d distance was considered equal to 1. Five textural features are measured from $D(i|\delta)$: contrast, angular second moment, entropy, mean, and inverse difference moment. As with the GLCM method, the assumption of an isotropic texture distribution inside the aneurysm sac was considered, consequently averaging over the four angular directions was computed.

Feature Selection.

Two methods were employed for the feature selection process: one based on the statistical estimation of p value through Student t test and the other one by observing the change in classification efficiency through a sequential forward selection (SFS) algorithm. In the last case, the SFS method has been based on Linear Discriminant Analysis (LDA) and K -nearest neighbor classifiers. The optimal features selected by the combination of both methods were: energy, inertia, entropy, inverse difference moment, sum average, sum variance from GLCM features, long run emphasis, run length non-uniformity from GLRLM features, contrast, and angular second moment from GLDM features.

2.3 Classification

Three different computer-aided diagnosis strategies (Fig 2) were developed for comparative purposes. The first one, *cad1* (Fig 2a), consisted of three independent neural networks, each one using as input one of the three texture features vector types. A neural network with 13 input nodes for GLCM method, another with 11 input nodes for GLRLM method, and another one with 5 input nodes for GLDM method were implemented.

The type of neural network employed was a three-layer backpropagation. The structure for each neural network consisted of the mentioned number of neurons on the input layer, one hidden layer, and an output layer with one neuron. A nonlinear sigmoid function with 0 and 1 saturation values is used as the activation function for each neuron, both the hidden layer and the output layer. The backpropagation algorithm with adaptive learning rate and momentum was used for neural networks training. In order to find the appropriate number of hidden neurons, and the values of learning rate and momentum for each neural network, a trial-and-error process was applied. Finally, a hidden layer of 20 neurons for the GLCM and the RLM features and 10 neurons for the GLDM features were found appropriate. To evaluate the network performances during the training and testing processes, the criterion was the mean square error.

The second alternative, cad2 (Fig 2b), consists of an individual neural network with the same inputs as the number of features obtained by the feature selection process. The type of neural network, internal structure and training conditions were maintained as in the first CAD system. A hidden layer of 10 neurons was found appropriate by a trial-and-error process.

The third classification scheme, cads3 (Fig 2c), consists of an ensembles of three neural networks, each using as input one of the three feature vector types (GLCM, RLM, and GLDM). The final decision of the system is generated by combining the diagnostic outputs of individual NN through a majority voting scheme [18]. The internal NN structures were kept the same than in the first architecture.

Fig. 1. Implemented CAD schemes, (a) cad1, (b) cad2, and (c) cad3.

3 Results

In order to evaluate the potential of texture analysis based CAD systems to classify between the two types of aneurysm evolution the development and validation of the neural network structures has been based on the 10-fold cross validation method. To improve the evaluation of performance of the feature sets, the 10-fold cross validation was repeated 6 times, averaging the results. The average of total percent of correctly classified cases (accuracy) for all the trials was used as an estimate of the performance of each classifier. Table 2 shows the accuracy values (mean \pm standard deviation) estimated by the 10-fold cross validation of the training and testing sets of each classifier strategy.

Table 2. Mean and standard deviation values for classification accuracy (in %) for training and testing sets of the three CAD architectures.

Classifier		Accuracy (%) - training	Accuracy (%) - testing
cad1	GLCM	93.70 \pm 0.002	91.53 \pm 0.006
	GLRLM	80.23 \pm 0.035	79.42 \pm 0.026
	GLDM	90.11 \pm 0.006	88.38 \pm 0.008
cad2		94.37 \pm 0.005	93.13 \pm 0.007
cad3		97.23 \pm 0.002	96.38 \pm 0.005

From the Table 2 it is shown that the ensembles of classifiers architecture yielded to the best performance (96.38% \pm 0.005) followed by a 93.13% \pm 0.007 obtained with the feature selection alternative and a 91.53% \pm 0.006, 79.42% \pm 0.026, 88.38% \pm 0.008, from GLCM, GLRLM and GLDM texture methods respectively.

Receiver Operating Characteristics (ROC) curve (Fig 2) and area under the ROC curve (A_z) were also used as a measure of the classification performance. Table 3 presents the A_z values (mean \pm standard deviation) calculated for training and testing feature sets using the 10-fold cross validation.

Table 3. A_z values (mean \pm standard deviation) calculated for training and testing sets using the 10-fold cross validation.

Classifier		A_z mean training	A_z mean testing
cad1	GLCM	0.963 \pm 0.003	0.940 \pm 0.005
	GLRLM	0.868 \pm 0.005	0.821 \pm 0.007
	GLDM	0.945 \pm 0.003	0.915 \pm 0.005
cad2		0.974 \pm 0.002	0.952 \pm 0.005
cad3		0.983 \pm 0.001	0.971 \pm 0.005

The achieved values show again that the greatest area under the ROC curve, and consequently the best performance of the classifier is obtained with the multiple classifiers architecture ($A_z = 0.971 \pm 0.005$) followed by the feature selection scheme ($A_z = 0.952 \pm 0.005$) and GLCM, GLRLM and GLDM individual classifiers ($A_z = 0.940 \pm 0.005$, $A_z = 0.821 \pm 0.007$, $A_z = 0.915 \pm 0.005$ respectively).

Fig. 2. ROC curves for cad1-GLCM ($\diamond\diamond\diamond$), cad1-GLRLM($***$), cad1-GLDM(\dots), cad2($\blacksquare\blacksquare\blacksquare$), cad3(—)

According to the results in Table 2 and 3, cad3 can be considered as the most appropriate CAD architecture for discriminating the aneurysm evolution. The better performance of this architecture can be explained on the basis of an ensemble of classifiers allows exploitation of complementary information content in the different input sets and because multiple classifier systems generalize better than single ones [18].

It is worth noting that cad2 alternative performs better than any of the base-level classifiers although does not reach cad3 results. This is probably due to the greater dimension of the feature set fed into the cad2 scheme, allowing that different feature subsets interact with each other.

Conclusions

In the present study we have analysed the capacity of CAD systems based on textures analysis for classifying evolutions experimented by aorta aneurysms treated by EVAR. For this purpose, texture parameters have been extracted by three different methods, GLCM, GRLM, and GLDM. At the same time, three different classification strategies have been proposed for the implementation of the CAD system: independent neural networks for each texture feature set, a neural network fed by a selection of features, and an ensembles of three neural networks with a majority voting scheme for

obtaining the output. The best mean classification accuracy was achieved by the ensembles of classifiers ($95.48\% \pm 0.005$).

As a conclusion, it can be considered that the CAD system proposed could be used as a second opinion tool for assisting physicians in characterization of aneurysm evolution after EVAR treatment. However, taking into account the limited number of patients, further investigations will be needed to assess the potential of the system as a clinical tool.

References

1. Thompson MM: Controlling the expansion of abdominal Aneurysm. *Br. J. Surg* 2003; 90:897-898.
2. S. William Stavropoulos and Sridhar R. Charagundla: Imaging Techniques for Detection and Management of Endoleaks after Endovascular Aortic Aneurysm Repair, *Radiology*, June 2007; 243: 641 - 655.
3. G. García, J. Maiora, A. Tapia, M. De Blas. Evaluation of texture for classification of abdominal aortic aneurysm after endovascular repair. *Journal of Medical Imaging*. 2012; 25(3); 369-376.
4. Bashir, Mustafa R., Ferral, Hector, Jacobs, Chad, McCarthy, Walter, Goldin, Marshall Endoleaks After Endovascular Abdominal Aortic Aneurysm Repair: Management Strategies According to CT Findings *Am. J. Roentgenol*. 2009 192: W178-186.
5. Computer-Aided Diagnosis in Medical Imaging: Historical Review, Current Status and Future Potential. Kunio Doi. *Comput Med Imaging Graph*. 2007; 31(4-5): 198–211.
6. Morton MJ, Whaley DH, Brandt KR, Amrami KK. Screening mammograms: interpretation with computer-aided detection-prospective evaluation. *Radiology* 2006;239:375–383.
7. Boniha L, Kobayashi E, Castellano G, Coelho G, Tinois E, Cendes F, et al. Texture analysis of hippocampal sclerosis. *Epilepsia* 2003;44: 1546–50.
8. Arimura H, Li Q, Korogi Y, Hirai T, Abe H, Yamashita Y, Katsuragawa S, Ikeda R, Doi K. Automated computerized scheme for detection of unruptured intracranial aneurysms in threedimensional MRA. *Acad Radiol* 2004;11:1093–1104.
9. Jianguo Zhang, Tieniu Tan, Brief review of invariant texture analysis methods, *Pattern Recognition*, Volume 35, Issue 3, March 2002, Pages 735-747, ISSN 0031-3203.
10. Haralick, R., Shanmugam, K., Dinstein, I.: Textural features for image classification. *IEEE Transactions on Systems, Man, and Cybernetics SMC-3* (1973), 610–621.
11. R. M. M. Galloway, "Texture analysis using gray level run lengths," *Comput. Graphic. Image Processing*, vol. 4, pp. 172–179, 1975.
12. J. S. Weszka, C. R. Dyer, and A. Rosenfeld, "A comparative study of texture measures for terrain classification," *IEEE Trans. Syst., Man, Cybern.*, vol. SMC-6, pp. 269–285, Apr. 1976.
13. Mir, A.H.; Hanmandlu, M.; Tandon, S.N.; , "Texture analysis of CT images," *Engineering in Medicine and Biology Magazine, IEEE* , vol.14, no.6, pp.781-786, Nov/Dec 1995.

14. Gibbs P, Turnbull LW. Textural analysis of contrast-enhanced MR images of the breast. *Magn Reson Med* 2003; 50:92–98.
15. Nikita A, Nikita KS, Mougiakakou SG, Valavanis IK. In: Evaluation of texture features in hepatic tissue characterization from non-enhanced CT images. *Engineering in medicine and biology society, 2007. EMBS 2007. 29th annual international conference of the IEEE; 2007.* p. 3741-4.
16. Sboner A, Eccher C, Blanzieri E, Bauer P, Cristofolini M, Zumiani G, et al. A multiple classifier system for early melanoma diagnosis. *Artif Intell Med* 2003;27(1):29–44.
17. Jerebko AK, Malley JD, Franaszek M, Summers RM. Multiple neural network classification scheme for detection of colonic polyps in CT colonography data sets. *Acad Radiol* 2003;10(2):154–60.
18. Roli F, Giacinto G, Vernazza G. Methods for designing multiple classifier systems. In: Roli F, Kittler J, editors. *Proceedings of 2nd international workshop on multiple classifier systems in volume 2096 of lecture notes in computer science.* London, UK: Springer Verlag; 2001. p. 78–87.